

THE IMPORTANCE AND MAIN FUNCTIONS OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN IMPROVING THE METHODOICAL TRAINING OF SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article improving methodical training of school teachers the role of innovative activity is discussed. The relevance of today's teacher training especially determined by the fact that the teacher is the main person. Improving the professional knowledge and training of modern school teachers, enriching students' personal experiences, the conditions for effective implementation of innovative activities in preparing them for social life are highlighted.*

Keywords: *innovative activity, self-activation, creativity, creative activity*

In today's conditions, training highly qualified personnel should be carried out on the basis of modern systems and new pedagogical technologies. The essence of new pedagogical technologies is that the educational process is planned and implemented, which guarantees the achievement of the goals set for it.

The effective implementation of the teacher's innovative activity depends on a number of conditions. It includes the effective communication of the pedagogue, his attitude towards the opposite opinions, his readiness to express the recognition of the rational situation in various situations. As a result, the teacher will have a comprehensive motivation that will ensure knowledge and scientific activity.

The motivations of self-activation, self-knowledge and creativity gain importance in pedagogical activity, which allows to form the activity of creativity of the pedagogue. An important condition for innovation is the creation of a new situation of communication. The new situation of communication is the pedagogue's position of independence, pedagogical science, ability to create a new attitude towards himself.

One of the conditions for the innovative activity of the model of communication between the teacher and the student, the innovative activity is explained by the following main functions;

- conscious analysis of professional activity,
- a critical approach to norms,
- readiness for professional news,
- realization of opportunities, embodying one's lifestyle aspirations in one's professional activity.

In the conditions of current society, culture and educational development, the need for innovative activities of the pedagogue is measured by the following:

1. Socio-economic renewal requires a fundamental renewal of the educational system, methodology and technology of the educational process, it consists in the creation, assimilation and use of new innovations;

2. Humanization of educational content always requires the search for new critical forms of teaching and technologies.

3. Character and change of the teacher in relation to mastering the pedagogical innovation and its implementation.

The teacher appears as the author, researcher, user and promoter of new pedagogical technologies, theories, concepts.

The analysis of the teacher's innovative activity requires the use of certain criteria that determine the effectiveness of innovation. Such criteria include the acceptability of teacher innovation, high efficiency, and the possibility of creative application of innovation in public experiments.

The innovative activity of the pedagogic includes the analysis and evaluation of the innovation, the formation of the purpose and concept of future actions. Implementation and analysis of this plan includes evaluation of effectiveness, in which the effectiveness of innovative activities is determined by the personality of the pedagogue.

The main features of the teacher's ability to innovate:

- the person's use of creative motivation. This is the pedagogue's curiosity, creative interest, creative achievements, striving for leadership and self-improvement;
- creativity, this is an imaginative vision, the ability to evaluate and strive for self-improvement;
- the ability to evaluate professional activity, acquire creative activity and pedagogical research methods;
- the individual ability of the teacher, this is creative activity and work ability, perseverance, responsibility and honesty, self-control.

Research of innovative activity allows to determine the criteria of teacher's sensitivity to innovative activity:

- determining the need for innovative activity;
- preparation for involvement in creative activities;
- alignment of personal goals with innovative activities;
- preparation for overcoming creative failures;
- impact of innovative activity on professional independence.

Innovative activity consists of motivational, technological and reflexive parts. The preparation of the teacher for this activity is increased in two directions: formation of innovative preparation for the perception of novelty and teaching to act in a new way.

Students' cognitive activity and its management are of particular importance in the organization of innovation activities.

The study of the pedagogical bases of the functions, mechanisms of innovation processes and the technologies of its implementation and management principles provides an opportunity to organize the educational process based on the achievements of modern pedagogy and psychology.

In conclusion, increasing the efficiency of the educational process, forming strong theoretical knowledge, activities, skills and competences of learners, and ensuring their transformation into professional skills, the use of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching process is the demand of the times and the quality of social necessity. is being placed.

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